

Rebuttal Letter to manuscript ADWR_2016_136:

“Estimating the water budget components and their variability in a Pre-Alpine basin with JGrass-NewAGE”

Wuletawu Abera; Giuseppe Formetta; Marco Borga and Riccardo Rigon

Dear Editor Professor Graham Sander, and dear reviewers,

We would like to thank you for your comments and suggestions, which gave us the opportunity to improve the paper. In the revised manuscript (MS), we hope to solve all the issues raised. In this document we answer to all the questions raised by the reviewers. Comments are shown in bold font, followed by our answer/comment in normal font. The major corrections/changes in the manuscript are displayed in red font.

Editor’s comment:

Dear Dr Abera,

Three reviews are now available for your paper "Estimating the water budget components and their variability in a Pre-Alpine basin with JGrass-NewAGE". Two reviewers, although recognizing the potential interest of your work, address several issues to be handled before the paper can be published. A third reviewer suggests moderate revision only.

The main issues to be handled are, in my opinion:

- 1. The novel contribution of the paper needs to be highlighted better in the paper. In this work little additional methodological development was made. If the novel contribution of the paper is not convincingly described, I would recommend the rejection of the paper.**
- 2. The paper structure, especially in the introduction and methodology, needs to be improved. Many figures need to be improved as well.**
- 3. A weak point of the study is the lack of verification of ET with an outlier for ET in November. The outlier needs to be explained and if alternative approaches for ET-verification could be found, this would strengthen the paper.**
- 4. It should be explained how systematic underestimation of precipitation by rain gauges was handled.**
- 5. A more physically based interpretation and selection of the interpolation methods is needed.**

6. It is expected that a 400m height difference would result in significant average temperature differences, which are neglected now. This needs additional attention.

As a conclusion, I suggest the editor major revision and additional review for your manuscript and look forward to a revised version.

Dear Editor,

We thank you for the comment given to our MS which obviously further improves the quality of our paper. We revised the MS for emphasizing the novelties of our efforts. Though the methodologies used are already described in various studies in modeling a specific hydrological process, we believe that the main contribution concerns the reconfiguration of those methods to solving water budget at catchment scale and sub-daily time steps. The methodology proposed for the estimation evapotranspiration at basin scale, with no in-situ observation, is another addition to this MS. The way we estimate the separation of snowfall from rainfall is also new. Besides, we systematically produced an effort to give thee errors of estimations, which are usually missing in hydrological literature. It was certainly our fault if we failed to make these points clear, and we will try to improve the concepts in the revised manuscript.

Being specific on the points you raised:

#2. We revised the introduction according to the comments given review #2 (General comment) and the figures for clarity.

#3. We do not have estimates of actual ET in that basin. That's the reason we used what we called the Budyko Hypothesis. Being sincere, ET estimation, even when they use modern techniques of sonic anemometry, can be very error prone (as, for instance, can be verified from Hingerl et al., 2016), therefore sticking with mass conservation is still a valuable option, at least at basin scale. But following this recommendation, we used GLEAM evapotranspiration satellite data (Martens et al., 2016) to compare with our results. Regards November outliers, it is a mistake we made during plotting the simulation results. We are sorry for this; we corrected this in the revised MS.

#4 - As we specified we assumed that rainfall measurements were correct. According to the undercatch theories and measurements campaign, rainfall is underestimated of about 2 to 5% in average, with dependence on various factors, but mainly to wind. Assuming then a sound formula for the dependence of the undercatch with wind, such as a linear regression, we should first interpolate wind measures (that we do not have at the moment, otherwise we should have used probably Penman-Monteith instead of Priestley-Taylor

for evapotranspiration). While this is the general point on the influences of rainfall measurement error on hydrological modeling studies, the accuracy of the raingauge measurements for the study basin has been assessed in the frame of several studies, and no systematic underestimation was noted and reported. Some of these studies aimed to use raingauge data as benchmark for remote sensed estimation of rainfall, either by use of weather radar (Borga et al., 2000) and satellite (Brocca et al., 2015). Other studies aimed at the comparison of different throughfall collectors (Zuecco et al, 2014) and at the analysis of seasonal changes in runoff generation by using isotopic data (Penna et al., 2015). The following sentences are added to include these points in the revised MS:

“The accuracy of the raingauge measurements for the study basin has been assessed in the frame of several studies (Borga, 2002; Brocca et al., 2015; Penna et al., 2015), and no systematic over/underestimation was reported. In fact, the stations are used as benchmark for remote sensed estimation of rainfall, either by use of weather radar (Borga, 2002) and satellite (Brocca et al., 2015). Hence, the precipitation data, without measurement systematic bias correction, is interpolated from meteorological stations to points of interest (centroids of each HRU) using the spatial interpolation (NewAGE-SI) tools.”

#5 We used various kriging with the aim to improve precipitation estimation. To evaluate different rainfall estimation data obtained from different kriging tools, we used two strategies (1) using cross-validation and (2) discharge simulation. The former gives the accuracy of the estimates at a point scale, while the latter provides estimates of the data reproducing basin response (discharge). The interpretation of our results is that the kriging that reproduce the point scale precipitation better is not the same as the one reproduces basin response (discharge) better. In fact, the model is calibrated to each precipitation estimates, and the model calibration process might compensates for inadequate/abundant of precipitation data. Actually, similar results have shown before in literature (Ruelland et al., 2008).

#6 There are several options for sampling HRU temperature. One option is to further divide HRUs into different elevation bands. However, in our case, HRUs are really small and temperature at the centroids of each HRUs is a sufficiently realistic representation of the physical phenomenon. To show this, we have interpolated temperatures for each pixel in HRUs. Figure 1 shows through boxplots the distribution of temperature fields relative to 120 temperature maps and each HRU. The boxplot shows that the temperature distribution for most of the HRUs is mostly contained in half of a degree centigrade. Therefore, in this case, the use of single location estimates (with high savings of computational time) is representative values. We added this note in the revised MS.

Figure 1: box-and-whisker plot of standard deviation of temperature field distribution within each HRU, plotted against their mean elevations. A horizontal line inside the boxes indicates the median HRU temperature standard deviation. The upper and lower whiskers represent the 95% confidence interval distribution of the Inter-quartile range. Each box of the plots is calculated from 120 temperature maps sampled from all the seasons across all the years. It clearly shows that temperature spatial variation as given by LDK is limited in each HRU to a less than half a degree.

Reviewers' comment:

Reviewer #1:

Dear authors and Editor,

I have finished reviewing the paper entitled “Estimating the water budget components and their variability in a Pre-Alpine basin with JGrass-NewAGE” by Abera et al. I have found the paper very interesting. It is well written and structure, methods are clearly explained and results are thoroughly discussed. I think that the paper is dealing with issues that are of interest for the hydrology community, including rainfall/snow partitioning and evapotranspiration estimation for ungauged basins. The only major issue I found missing in the paper is the lack of a validation procedure for the ET method suggested by the authors. This can be done

for a gauged location (or for a small catchment for it the water budget, including ET, is known) that is different than the Posina River basin presented in here. Beside this issue I have listed a number of comments/suggestions below. I am recommending ‘moderate revision’ for this paper.

Dear reviewer #1, we thank you for the general appreciation of our work, and specific comments given that help to improve our manuscript. Regard to the ET validation using some in-situ observation, we argue that our effort is not validation of ET model using in-situ observation but evaluation of ET at basin scale. We agree that having some measurement could be of help, however obtaining (upscaling) ET at basin scale from ground-based measurements is a different challenge than getting a single measure, due to its high spatial variability (e.g. Xu and Singh, 2005; Xue et al., 2013), and having one single measure could be not so significant. Instead, our effort is to use in-situ discharge and precipitation measurements, which are relatively accurate integrated measures of basin fluxes, to come up with reasonable coarse grained estimation of ET and storage, and eventually close the water budget. However, in the revised MS, we compare our basin scale ET results with the one obtained by GLEAM satellite ET estimates (over a cell of 625 square kilometers superimposed to our basin) (Martens et al., 2016). Following this analysis, we have added the following paragraph in the methodology section:

“The primary verification of our ET estimation is its consistency with the rest of the water budget. However, for further evaluation of the results, at the whole basin scale, we used the Global Land Evaporation Amsterdam Methodology (GLEAM) (Miralles et al., 2011a), a global, satellite-based, ET data set. The performance of GLEAM is assessed positively in different studies (McCabe et al., 2016; Miralles et al., 2011b) and it is available at 0.25° spatial resolution and daily temporal resolution. For comparison, therefore, we aggregated NewAge ET estimation to daily time scale for the whole basin.”

and, in the result section, we have done comparative analysis between the two estimates, and the result is plotted in figure 12, and the following paragraph is added to discuss the results:

“A comparison of time series (aggregated at three time resolutions i.e. daily, monthly, and yearly) of NewAge ET with GLEAM estimates for whole basin is shown in figure 12 for 6 years (1995-2000). At daily time step, the correlation and the PBIAS between GLEAM and modelled ET are 0.82 and -35.7 respectively, whereas at monthly time step they are 0.9 and -55.5, respectively (figure 12). The comparison result shows that NewAGE ET is more variable than GLEAM ET. GLEAM clearly returns higher estimated values. From 1995-2000, the maximum annual difference between the two

estimations is about 180 mm in 1997, while the minimum is 50 mm in 1996. The basin scale difference is accumulating and gives a difference of 715 mm after the six years and is not compatible with the ground measurements, i.e. precipitation and discharge, we have.”

Specific comments

1. L52-56 “In this paper we describe a method, supported by innovative tools, for obtaining the budget under “standard conditions” i.e. when data available are total precipitation, discharge at some gauge station, and temperature”. – what is the temporal scale? Daily? Hourly?

The temporal scale for all the types simulations is hourly. In the revised MS, we added this information.

“Methodologies and ideas for determining routinely the water budget terms at hourly and subdaily time scale, based on the availability of a limited set of ground measures, i.e. rainfall, temperature and discharge in a few locations, are clearly not commonly developed. In this paper we describe a method to fill the literature gap.”

2. L58 “We take for granted that total precipitation amount can be estimated according to (Garen and Marks, 2005; Tobin et al., 2011; Abera, 2016)”. – after “to” something is missing (before referring to other papers).

Thank you, and we revised this into “according to the procedures presented in Garen and Marks (2005); Tobin et al. (2011), Abera (2016).

3. L61 “appropriately” – I am not sure this is the right word.

This word has been deleted.

4. L87 “The best approach to estimate ET at small (spatial and temporal) scale is based on models that use physical knowledge”. ‘High spatial and temporal resolution’ instead?

Now the phrase “high spatial and temporal resolution” is used.

5. L129 “HRU” is mentioned here for the first time. Do not use abbreviation.

Actually HRU is mentioned for the first time at L32, with full form i.e. “hydrological response unit (HRU)”. However we add also here for redundancy.

6. L136 “Alpine foothills” – please state the elevation differences at the catchment.

The elevation difference of the basin is 1820 meters, and this is added: “The elevation difference of the basin is 1820 meters.” in the revised MS.

7. L137 “the climate” – please provide addition information regarding the climate (e.g. what is the estimated snow contribution? How precipitation are divided on seasonal basis? Etc.).

Thank you. We added these information in the revised MS: “The climate is characterised as wet, with annual precipitation of 1740 mm and annual runoff of 1000 mm (Norbiato et al., 2008; Francois et al., Submitted). The long-term (30 years, 1986-2016) snowfall to precipitation ratio averages 20% (Francois et al., Submitted), ranging from 5% to 27% depending on years. There are two relative 160 maxima for monthly precipitation: one in April (163 mm) and one in October (240 mm).”

8. L152 “worth” – can be deleted.

True. It is deleted.

9. L161 “...they will not be fully re-discussed here” – that is OK, but I would give some additional information regarding each of the models/components (maybe in an Appendix?). You cannot expect a reader who is not familiar with your previous studies to read 6 papers before this one in order to understand your latest.

It is true that there are many papers cited about JGrass-NewAGE system. However, the components used in the papers are briefly described in the methodological sections. Following “...they will not be fully re-discussed here” sentence, we indicated that some of the models are described in respective sections i.e. at L169 “**The following sections provide the methods for each term of the water balance.....**”. For instance, basin partition (on section 3.1), kriging (in section 3.2), snow-rainfall separation (section 3.3), rainfall-runoff (section 3.4), evapotranspiration (section 3.5) etc provide enough information about the models. We added in the new revised manuscript some further description.

10. L165 “for longwave and shortwave radiation” – I guess only incoming radiation? Please indicate explicitly.

It is actually the net radiation, both the incoming and outgoing radiation. We revised it.

11. L198 “Id” – can be deleted.

We deleted “Id”

12. L206 (and repeated elsewhere) “the NewAGE” – ‘the’ is not needed.

Sure, we removed “the”.

13. L223 “so” – to?

Replaced by “to”.

14. Equation 2 – not all are function of time? If it is all depended on the time step t of the model than add (t) as supplement to the variables.

In the revised MS, the equation is rewritten as follows, now the variables are a function of time.

$$\begin{cases} J_R(t) = \alpha_r * \left[\frac{J(t)}{\pi} \cdot \arctan\left(\frac{T(t)-T_s(t)}{m_1}\right) + \frac{J(t)}{2} \right] \\ J_S(t) = \alpha_s * [J(t) - J_R(t)] \end{cases}$$

15. L278 “At the moment, a manual optimization procedure is used to determine Eq.(2) parameters” – why manual? You have objective functions to use.

There is a difference in time steps between the simulation output (i.e. hourly) and the available snow satellite observation (i.e. daily). At the moment, due to the lack of integrating various time steps inside JGrass-NewAge and for simplicity, we used manual calibration procedures. The following sentence is added:

“Due to the difference in time step of the NewAge simulation and MODIS data, a manual optimization procedure is used to determine the parameters of Eq.(2).”

15. L303 are the indexes somehow weighted?

The primary objective function is accuracy index (AI). Hence, we tune the parameters primarily to optimize AI. Once we reach the maximum AI, maintaining the same AI value, we adjust the parameters to increase the rank correlation coefficient.

16. L322 how snow melt is consider?

It is just considered as input to the rainfall-runoff component for each HRU, as written in L326 and depicted in figure 2.

17. L326 and Moore 2007?

Yes, Moore (2007) is added.

18. L339 “complimentary material” – Supplementary Material? I was not able to access any additional material beside of the main manuscript.

Supplementary material is better phrase. We are sorry for the inconveniences; now we fix the link.

19. L345 “LUCA” – reference is needed.

We add a reference here, but we already given the reference to LUCA at L168.

20. L351 “hymod” – capital H

Thank you, corrected!

21. L363 “surface net radiation” – incoming shortwave and longwave radiation? Diffusive radiation? Please be more specific here.

Actually it is net radiation, which is estimated from the net shortwave radiation and net longwave radiation.

22. L371 “using kriging” – elevation depended kriging?

Yes, we used various krigings to estimate temperature, and based cross-validation, we select the best performing kriging. In this, Local Deternded Kriging (LDK) method, which uses elevation as auxiliary data, is used to interpolate temperature. In the revised MS, we added the type of kriging used in bracket (see L432)

23. L375 “and the internal temperature variability within each HRU has been checked to be less than half a degree Celsius” – checked how? Do you have stations within the HRU?

Based on cross-validation analysis of various kriging, we select the best performing kriging methods to estimate temperature spatially. To verify the appropriateness of selecting HRU centroid as representative or good approximation of temperature field, we interpolate temperature to each grid (raster) of the HRU for some selected time steps. This interpolated temperature field is analyzed to see variability within HRU. We find out that, at basin scale, the variability (i.e. standard deviation) of the long-term interpolated

temperature within HRU is less than half a degree Celsius. Please see Figure 1

24. L461 “The aggregation still maintains a relevant spatial variability in rainfall distribution, which is more than 70 mm for the represented event” – this sentence is not clear to me.

It is a sample to show the rainfall variability between the subbasins' HRU's obtained using the kriging procedures. Hence, we used some instant events, in addition to time series comparison, to observe accumulated effects at event scale. We revised this sentence for clarity as follows: “This operation is repeated for each time step, and for instance, figure 4 shown the spatial distribution of precipitation for a time instant event (16 October, 1996). The accumulated event rainfall maintains a relevant spatial distribution difference, which is more than 70 mm for the particular event presented in Figure.”

25. L633 “Our result suggests that taking the TB ~ 10 years would be a reasonable choice” – why?

The reason is described in the previous sentence: “the alpha is highly variable for the first ten years of simulation, subsequently becoming relatively stable around the mean for the remaining seven years (figure 13)”. To clarify this, we rephrased this in the revised MS as:

“..., the alpha is highly variable for the first ten years of simulation, subsequently becoming relatively stable around the mean for the remaining seven years (figure 13), suggesting that taking the TB ~ 10 years would be a reasonable choice.”

26. L640 “The errors of estimation can vary as much as 20%” – variability? Error compared to what?

It is the error of estimation. This combines the ET estimation of Priestley-Taylor using 17 alpha parameters, generated according to the years of closure, and the errors of inputs to estimate ET. It is estimated as in L480, which is generated from the error of precipitation, discharge, and the alpha parameter (in ET model).

27. L670 “ET varies from about 19% to 35%, Q from 64% to 95% and S from -19% to 5% of the whole yearly budget” – two issues: (1) please discuss how your results of the water budget fit water budget estimations for other catchments (nearby or catchments located in a similar climate); (2) negative S, what does it mean? Please explain explicitly in the text.

As a study in the Pre-alpine basin in North Italy, the results are obviously a sample case for the general water budget behavior of the region. Every basin is different and it is not correct to generalize these findings to other basins without further analysis. Having the same of dataset in any basin of the world, one can easily repeat the same analysis. However, to our knowledge such estimation has not been performed before by others in the nearby basin. Overall, we claim that actually the closure of the water budget is very rarely performed with the tools we used. In any ways, the findings of the paper can be the used as reference for similar (nearby) basins.

Regards to the negative storage change, it means that at a particular year the basin outflow (ET and Q) is higher than the inflow (J), which is possible because storage was accumulated in the previous years. To explain this, the following text is added in the revised MS:

“The negative storage changes, at the particular years, are most likely attributed to: 1) the amount, seasonal variability and nature of precipitation and/or 2) high atmospheric demand causing high evapotranspiration. It is essentially mean that outflow (ET and Q) is higher than the inflow (J), which is possible because storage was accumulated in the previous years.”

Appendix

28. Equation B.3 – should be “” instead of “BIAS”?

Corrected.

29. 1169 “MSE” – should be NSE?

We revised the sentence accordingly.

30. After equation C.4: “where, $nRH(t)$ and $R(t)$ and is direct and residual runoff according to Hymod procedure” – should be ‘where $RH(t)$ and $R(t)$ are direct and residual runoff, according to Hymod procedure’.

Revised accordingly.

Figures and tables

31. Figure 1 – You can use google Earth for fig 1a but than give them all the deserve credit and do not crop the image. Please add to it the label of the catchment, coordinates and scale. In the legend of b, replace ‘dem’ with elevation and delete ‘dem’ from the figure caption.

The figure is revised accordingly.

32. Figure 2, 3 and 4 – the fonts should be a little larger as it is hard to read. What are F.c, H.M, G.C., Exp and dat? If you want the reader to understand these charts than you need to explain the text somewhere.

In the revised MS, we combine figure 2, 3, and 4 together (see reviewer 3, specific comment 3) and improved the readability.

33. Figure 6 – please add units in the legend.

Added.

34. Figure 8 – consider adding the temperature time series to this figure, it might add some value to explain the rainfall/snow partitioning.

Thank you for the suggestion. We added the temperature record (please see figure 6 of the revised MS).

35. Figure 10 – reduce the size of the figure.

Revised accordingly.

36. Figure 11 – should not be presented as bar plot. Replace the bars with points to represent the mean.

Since we are presenting the long-term annual (18 years) runoff, here we argue that it is better to represent the variability with \pm bar plot, instead of just a mean value.

37. Table 3 – I am not sure this table is needed, you are stating all numbers in the main text anyhow

We combined this table with table 5 (in the revised MS it is in table 4)

Reviewer #2:

Review on "Estimating the water budget components and their variability in a Pre-Alpine basin with JGrass-NewAGE" by Abera et al.

The manuscript (MS) deals with the example application of the Model JGrass-NewAGE to a catchment at the southern edge of the alps and a practical solution for

problems such as meteo data interpolation in the process. It is very well written with only very few minor language issues, and mostly clear messages - exceptions mentioned in the detailed comments. Several figures require more care. The methodology is mostly sound, but several points like the centroid interpolation and the internal subbasin temperature and precipitation variability it might override, need clarification before the soundness can fully be judged (also contained in the detailed comments). I am unsure about whether the degree of originality is sufficient for *Adv Water Resour*: The MS would surely merit publication as a first publication of the model, but apparently this has already been done. With this background, application to a basin where reference ET measurements exist, or to a larger area where estimating the water budget components is of general interest to the community, would have been a more logical and relevant next step. That said, the MS definitely deserves publication somewhere in the scientific literature.

We thank reviewer #2 for his/her positive feedback and comments on our work. The novelty of our work includes the reasonable estimation of ET where there is no in-situ observation by using the closure of the water budget. Besides ET is highly complex processes, and even if point measurements were available they could be useless (for further point on this, please see answer for reviewer #1). Instead of comparing our ET estimate with a local measure, we compare our global result with the one obtained by remote GLEAM measure (over a cell of 625 square kilometers superimposed to our basin). It is true that we presented various technical aspects of the single model components in other papers. However, in this paper we apply all the submodels together, and produce time varying (multitemporal) fields of quantities (with the granularity of the HRUs). Among the new results we also assessed the error in our estimates, and verified with success the consistency of what we estimated in internal points of the catchment where we have discharge measurements.

L5-56: The motivation of the study in context of existing methods and their spatial scales is somewhat confusing and arbitrary. During the start of the introduction it appears that the authors aim at something different from more detailed approaches applicable only to small areas, then the topic is left for a while and near L44 the study is defined against large to global scale studies. In the course, in-situ measurements are mentioned twice (L5 and L47) but references, unlike for the other scales, are not given (as far as I could check the references near L5 involve satellite data or models, and there is no example for a purely in-situ based closure either where it is mentioned explicitly (L47), although some exist, e.g. with micrometeorological ET measurements (Högström and Larssen 1968, *Tellus* 20:633; Wilson et al. 2001, *Agric. Forest Meteorol.* 106:153; Graf et al. 2014, *Water Resour. Res.* 50: 4837). A more transparent approach would be: Describe the full spectrum

of methods / spatial scales of studies in one place (maybe with some of their advantages and disadvantages - not much more detailed or concise as now, but more systematically) and then place your own study in that spectrum, making clear if this particular scale / methodology is yet underexamined, and if not, what else makes the study important. The global abundance of "standard conditions" as mentioned now at L 54 is one good point in that respect, but remember that this doesn't mean that such a "standard" catchment makes an ideal site for a demonstration: The study could have been more relevant and a clearer progress in the context of the already published papers on your model, if it had been applied somewhere with existing ET measurements as reference, from which good conclusions could then be drawn with how much uncertainty it could be transferred to "standard" catchments.

We really appreciate the suggestion on the structure of the introduction section. Based on the given insight, we now reviewed almost all papers, about one hundred papers, which deals with the water budget at basin scale and restructured the introduction of our MS. Now the "introduction" of the MS is revised based on the available literatures and aims to show the efforts already done in the literature and the gaps that this MS can fill. We also added the list of the papers deals with the water budget at the end of the introduction.

1. L32: The concept of HRUs is explained only much later near L173.

Yes it is true. We provided a short definition of HRUs at this stage, and refer, in parenthesis, the section where it is explained in details. The following sentence is added:

"A HRU represents a part of the basin that can be treated as a single unit (see section 3.1)."

2. L78: "from now on..." was meant to be in parentheses?

We corrected accordingly.

3. L89: "a lot of" is quite vague, and most of those meteorological data are not that uncommon. Mention more clearly which variable(s) (probably radiation in the first place) inhibit using Penman-Monteith in many catchments (but also remember that e.g. radiation is explicitly or implicitly needed by almost any other approach). Note that aerodynamic and canopy resistance are no meteorological measured variables in the strict sense, and only needed if actual ET of a not yet charaterized vegetation (as opposed to grass reference ET0) is aimed at.

We rephrased to say it properly. Now revised to: "However, these models, such as

Penman-Monteith (Monteith et al., 1965), require more meteorological data than usually available in most basins, such as radiation, temperature, wind speed, air pressure, and aerodynamic and canopy resistance.”

4. L97: "we provide what we believe to be the unique way": Re-check, this is somewhat confusing, and sounds like a very strong claim (as far as I could find without justification thereafter).

It is our believe that our approach is novel or innovative because it provides, for the first time as far as our knowledge, a method that allows estimating ET and storage, hence close the water budget at high temporal and spatial resolution with just few in-situ precipitation and discharge observations. Anyway, we revised the sentence to “play down” this a little bit (see the suggestion by reviewer #3, comment 16):

“We provide a way to close water budget in the absence of ET and water storage measurements based on the combination of Priestley-Taylor (Priestley and Taylor, 1972) and Budyko hypothesis (Budyko, 1978) at any space-time scale.”

5. L142: "hydrometer" - you mean runoff gauges? Use clearer term or explain on first mentioning. Also some short information of the particular measurement technique would be good, to get a better idea of the reliability of the runoff estimates.

We changed the term into “streamgauges”. We added a sentence about the discharge measurement techniques:

“..... and hourly discharge data is collected by means of an ultrasound sensor. The rating curve is updated twice per year by using current meters and Doppler methods for the flow velocity measurements.”

6. L155: This sentence in various forms is repeated very often, use the model name where needed for clarity, not excessively for advertising.

In the revised MS, we revised for such kind of excessive uses of terms.

7. L172 (title 3.1): partitioning?

We changed into “Watershed partitioning”.

8. L184 and Fig. 1: Given the size and topography of the subbasins shown in Fig. 1, it can hardly be justified to use the term synonymously with hillslope. Add scale

bars to both figures and adjust their height to each other. How was the small non-drained, non-numbered subbasin in the north treated in the overall budget (e.g. was its area included in the total study area)? The figure indicates that we have at least 400 m of altitude difference inside some of the subbasins - see next comment and the one on L371.

We revised the text of the revised MS using subbasin instead of hillslope. The small non-drained cells in the north are included neither in the budget nor in the total area.

9. L204: Make clear already here which of both methods (centroids or smaller cells) was used. From the rest of the text it seems that it were the centroids. Note that once you decide the study is mainly about your application and not about the (already published) model, making clear what you actually did has priority over mentioning what else you could have done with the model (applies to several other places of the MS as well). Given the size and large internal altitude difference (see last comment) of the subbasins, I wonder why the centroid solution was chosen, and what might have been the effect on uncertainty?

We revised the new manuscript accordingly to reviewer note. For what regards the variable, we used centroids for both interpolation of precipitation and temperature to each HRU. We believe that an area of 2.6 km² is not so large, and a single point sample can be sufficient to capture the spatial variability inside each catchment and is an effective choice for simulations at hourly time steps. Due to the sensitivity of temperature data with elevation and being the main input for snow model, we have checked the internal variability of the temperature field by interpolated at each grid of the HRU. Please, also see the answer to specific comment 23 for reviewer #1 and the comment to the editor arguments.

10. L324-339: The term Hymod is not explained upon first mentioning, and it is unclear whether the "complimentary material" mentioned at the end of the paragraph relates to the appendix, one of the places mentioned in the last section "Code availability", or something else altogether.

In the revised MS, more explanation about Hymod is added in the supplementary materials.

11. L278: e.g. ...is used to determine the parameters of Eq. (2).

Thank you. We have revised this sentence accordingly.

12. L369: "can be" or "was" (in your study)?

Revised accordingly i.e. replaced by "is".

13. L371-376: Again, the combination of comparatively coarsely defined subbasins with a centroid-based solution to the meteo parameter interpolation method does not appear very lucky. You claim that temperature differences were checked to be below 0.5 K (how?). But the abovementioned ≥ 400 m topography inside a subbasin estimated from the figure, along with usual atmospheric temperature gradients, suggests differences of at least 2 K.

The same question was raised and we were happy to double check this. In any ways, please see the reply to comment 8. And also see figure 1 on how we check the internal variability of interpolated temperature.

14. L450-455: Discussion of the figure is somewhat unclear. Make clearer e.g. whether the observation that the differences are between the Krigung methods and not so much between the semivariogram fittings relates to all three measures or just some (the order of text somehow suggests that it is only/particularly true for ME, which I could not verify).

Thank you, the text is not clear here. We revised as follows:

“The results of the mean error value are found to be some inconsistent with the reports from the previous two performance indicators. It shows some differences between the semivariogram fittings within a kriging method (figure 3c). However, comparing across all 16 interpolations, the main difference is observed between the kriging methods, not between the semivariogram fitting within a single model (Haberlandt, 2007).”

15. L464: Make clearer if this distribution is particular for this period, or a general observation throughout the catchment.

Yes, this is clearly for the particular period, and hence, we revised it for clarity: “The accumulated event rainfall still maintains a relevant spatial distribution, which is more than 70 mm for this particular event”.

16. L468: The reader is somewhat puzzled at this point since it is not mentioned which method was finally chosen, and learns only much later why. Maybe this can be solved by referring to that place here (L576).

It is true that we missed a final remark on comparison of the kriging tools to estimate precipitation in this line. Hence, we added a sentence to conclude the comparison results: “In general, the cross-validation results show that LOK and LDK (particularly LOK) outperforms OK and DK.”. The one referred by the reviewer (L576), however, is not for precipitation estimation, but for discharge estimation.

17. Section 4.1 in general: Was there any correction applied for the systematic underestimation of precipitation by the rain gauges? If not, how might it have affected the water budget estimation? Could it be that it caused artificially low ET variability as mentioned near L676, and/or the surprising result that DK was better than LOK in the overall ranking?

We did not apply correction for rain gauges. Accordingly to literature, this error is between 2 and 5 % of the estimate in average. Clearly an increase of, say 5% of rainfall, would affect: i) Adige model’s parameters; 2) Recharge and ET that would be both increased. We do not think this can have any relation with the kriging outputs.

However, as to our study basin, the accuracy of the raingauge measurements has been assessed in the frame of several studies, and no systematic underestimation was noted and reported. Some of these studies aimed to use raingauge data as benchmark for remote sensed estimation of rainfall, either by use of weather radar (Borga et al., 2000) and satellite (Brocca et al., 2015). Other studies aimed at the comparison of different throughfall collectors (Zuecco et al, 2014) and at the analysis of seasonal changes in runoff generation by using isotopic data (Penna et al., 2015). The following sentences are added to include these points in the revised MS:

“The accuracy of the raingauge measurements for the study basin has been assessed in the frame of several studies (Borga, 2002; Brocca et al., 2015; Penna et al., 2015), and no systematic over/underestimation was reported. In fact, the stations are used as benchmark for remote sensed estimation of rainfall, either by use of weather radar (Borga, 2002) and satellite (Brocca et al., 2015). Hence, the precipitation data, without measurement systematic bias correction, is interpolated from meteorological stations to points of interest (centroids of each HRU) using the spatial interpolation (NewAGE-SI) tools.”

18. L474: column of maps

“s’ is added.

19. Fig. 9: With the current layout it is very hard to compare the modeled lines

(model?) and dots (MODIS?) and also the caption is not clear about this layout. Maybe try a wider figure, thinner lines, and a legend or a more verbose caption.

In the revised MS, the figure is revised.

20. L571: The abbreviation PBIAS is only explained in the table caption and GOF only in the appendix, making this text hard to read.

The abbreviation of GOF is explained before in the text (L396). We add citation to the appendix but also explain the meaning of the abbreviation here. Please see reviewer 3, specific comment 55.

21. Fig. 10: Lines too thick, legend overlaps grey title bar, X axis texts (dates) overlap. Maybe it would also be interesting to use the same scale for the Y axes (making the upper row of subfigures larger and the lower one smaller) to get a better first glance on the importance of residuals with respect to discharge, now it looks "worse" than it is.

We revised this plot for clarity.

22. L674: In addition to what is mentioned in the comment on section 4.1, can this smoothness also be caused by the problem of determining both soil moisture and ET which depend on each other, as mentioned in the Appendix?

We do not believe so. The reasons we mentioned in the paper, we think is the reason. Two further aspects can cause variability. One would be to keep track of the energy budget, which could make to emerge some more heterogeneity (but energy input is already partially accounted for, since evapotranspiration is driven by radiation). The other would be account for vegetation dynamics and variability. Obviously these two causes would require further modeling components and parameters to calibrate. To emphasis this possible improvements, we have added the following sentences in the “conclusion” section:

“.....This study would benefit of further investigations on: 1) the effect of basin partitioning; 2) the use of a full energy budget component; and 3) an effective treatment of vegetation heterogeneity and dynamics.”

23. L680: Check embedding of citations (use parentheses or additional text).

We used parenthesis for embedding all citations.

24. Fig. 14: These diurnal cycles look much smoother than reality (at best, like a cloud-free period) and I'm not sure if I missed it, but is the temporal resolution of input data and modelling documented well enough to understand this smoothness?

In fact we did not use cloud cover in this study because this information was missing. However, we think the estimations remains reasonably correct.

25. L793: This is not completely consistent with L628 where the alpha estimate is said to be at the lower end of literature values.

Yes, true. In this case, however, we introduced a local water limit to evapotranspiration. This actually change the game and reverse the value of alpha making it higher that the average.

26. L804: "insisting": check wording

It is replaced by “dominates”

27. L820: "will be": should be replaced by "is" in case of (and at time of) publication.

Yes we changed “will be” to “is”.

28. L910: What is the difference between the Formetta 2013 a and b references?

Thank you for spotting this. They are the same and we revised it.

Reviewer #3:

The authors presents an interesting application of the open source JGrass-NewAGE modeling framework. In particular, they apply the model to estimate the water budget components in a Pre-Alpine basin. The paper also provide a comparison of different kriging interpolation methods (OK, LOK, DK, LDK), together with a discussion on MODIS imagery data for rainfall-snowfall separation and calibration-validation strategies for ET, rainfall and runoff.

Overall the manuscript provides useful information/results and is of interest for the audience of this journal. However, I found the manuscript difficult to read, especially in the Introduction and Methodology sections. The paper contains a great amount of information that needs to be better structured in order to help the reader

going through the manuscript's content and clarify objectives/methodology/results. Also, figures need to be improved (low quality, font too small, etc).

1. I suggest a number of “editorial” changes (see specific comments below) but the manuscript needs to be thoroughly revised. Regarding the results presented in this paper, I have serious problems with the assessment of the kriging methods and, especially, with Fig. 16.

Dear reviewer #3, we thank you for the general suggestions and comments given on our work. In the revised MS, we used all the comments given to improve the readability of the MS. In addition, we revised the introduction and methodology section of the MS for clarity. To improve the quality of the figures, we also re-draw the figures following the specific comments given by all the reviewers. Regarding November outliers, it is a mistake we made during plotting simulation results. We are sorry for this fact that should have never happened. We corrected the Figure in the revised MS.

2. In the case of kriging the authors state that “OK and LOK performed better than DK and LDK in detecting the total mass of water that fell in the basin. However, as we have seen, DK and LDK perform better in producing runoff”. This point is unclear to me and the author does not discuss further. The authors switch from using one interpolated field to another as if the choice of the method depended on the variable they want to investigate. In other words, the “best” interpolated rainfall field (which should be unique) is not clearly provided, leaving unsolved (and unclear) the problem of estimating rainfall – i.e. the basis for estimating the water budget components. Physical reasoning and critical analysis of kriging methods and the hydrological model is needed to assess the results - the choice of the “best” scenario seems “dynamic” at the moment, based on limited statistical analysis. The fact that calibration of discharge data perform better with a precipitation field that is different from the “best one” may indicate either that rainfall interpolation is highly uncertain or that the discharge model is.

We are sorry that we were not so clear in our explanation and we will try our best to be as clear as possible in the revised manuscript. Kriging is a linear interpolator of data. Despite much fuzziness has been raised around them, they are just a little more complicate than doing a linear regression, just because the linear regression coefficients here are made function of the semivariogram (or the covariances) between the data. Our tools, estimate these semivariogram separately from the whole process. So, the first action is to estimate these semivariograms on a sample data set. In this phase, we select among four possible different semivariogram shapes, the one that best fit the experimental semivariogram. The second phase is to use these semivariogram shapes,

kept fixed, for obtaining the real interpolation of the data. This second phase has some alternative, simple kriging (where the mean of the field is assumed to be known), ordinary kriging (where the mean of the field is unknown) are two of them.

We also added detrended kriging, which is actually a decomposition of the data signal in a linear component, dependent on elevation, and the residual. In detrended kriging (somewhere else also called kriging with external drift) the ordinary kriging is performed on these residuals, while the trend regression requires the determination of some further parameters.

So a statistical study is performed to see which one of the semivariogram is best and which of the krigings performs better. Obviously, the scope of the kriging is not to forecast future rainfall, but to extend spatially the knowledge acquired from meteorological stations. Our conclusion is that there are no significant variations in interpolation performances between OK and DK, even if their local version works better. For this reason, in simulating discharges, we used all the four types of krigings and check if any difference appears.

Discharge simulations imply a second step, and differentiated, parameter calibration procedure that gave the result that DK jointly with the modeling solution designed performs better than the other. This is in agreement with other literature (Ruelland et al., 2008), but we have no idea why this happens. We conjectured that, even if the “best performances” are not visible at the level of rainfall alone, the small differences in the statistical structure of spatial precipitation are amplified by the topology of the river network and the spatial organisation of the HRUs. Further studies and confirmation would be required, however, to make the conjecture on solid bases.

3. In the case of Fig. 16, simulated ET seems to be unrealistic: a strange peak in November is illustrated but completely ignored by the authors (“[ET] is highest in June and July and lowest from November to February, as expected”). The November peak is 3 times higher than summertime ET fluxes, thus strongly influencing annual estimates as well. If this is not a mistake (e.g. wrong plot, legend, label) it poses serious doubts about the accuracy of the simulations, undermining the whole water budget (and thus the paper).

Please see the answer to major comment 1.

In this regard, the author should provide references for the validity of the null-storage hypothesis and the values of alpha used in the literature (and maybe discuss why not using other approaches based on soil properties and water-stress relations).

The null storage hypothesis is made and has been made in all the approaches that use Budyko curve, so we can cite Budyko paper and the many followers. Please see specific comment 2.

In conclusion, I think that the paper is interesting but the authors needs to address a few important issues before the paper is considered for publication by this journal.

Thank you; hope we solved all issues raised.

Specific Comments

1. I understand the rationale for using HRU but the approach simplifies (a lot) processes such as groundwater flow (among others). Given the connections between groundwater flow and transpiration, I think it's worth adding a discussion on the topic (see for example: Maxwell and Condon (2016), Connections between groundwater flow and transpiration partitioning, Science 377-380).

We thank the reviewer to have brought our attention to Maxwell and Condon (MC) interesting paper. Interaction with groundwater is contemplated, even if in a simplified way, using reservoirs, and a non-linear rule for partitioning water between groundwater and surface water. Evapotranspiration, in turn, is limited by water quantity in the groundwater. The approach is simplified and could be considered unjustifiably simple compared to the one in MC. However, this is not truly the case because, in their continental wide simulation MC used grid cells of 1 square kilometer, thus reducing a lot the physical significance of the process-based groundwater laws they use for moving water around. The issue is interesting, but we do not believe it can be raised in this manuscript. We cite instead the MC paper in the revised Introduction as a valuable example of water budget closure and its insight on the connection between ETP and groundwater flow.

2. References for the “Budyko’s time” and the typical values of alpha are needed.

Budyko hypothesis in literature is used to estimate long-term water balance by assuming that the primary controls of ET are the local interaction of water supply (precipitation) and demand (potential evapotranspiration). Various applications of Budyko hypothesis to estimate annual and seasonal water balance are cited in Wang and Zhou (2016) and Yang et al. (2007). A reference for Budyko hypothesis general is already given, but “Budyko’s time” and the alpha connected to Budyko hypothesis to estimate high spatial and temporal resolution does not exist in literature. It is what we formalized in this MS.

3. Figures needs to be improved: conceptual models are not very clear, labels are difficult to read, etc (see other comments below)

We combined the three conceptual diagrams (figure 2, 3, and 4) per the suggestion of reviewer 1 (see specific comment 32).

4.The authors refer to some “complimentary material” (e.g. line 258) that was not provided.

Now we added the materials.

5.Abstract: no need to define the abbreviations J and Q at the end of the abstract

We revised it accordingly.

6.Eq. 1: I would probably use different subscript for Q_{ki} and Q_k (as in Formetta et al. 2011 for example). Also the term runoff usually refer to surface runoff and does not include groundwater (“output discharge from k-th link” as explained in Formetta et al. 2011 is probably more correct)

The water budget closure equation is usually presented in this form, and for consistency, we prefer to maintain the form we implemented.

7.Line 38: Q_i s are defined as output here, as input in Eq. 1. This is confusing, clarify

Thank you. It is true that there is error in this sentence. Q_i s are inputs to the control volume, and now we correct this.

8.Line 49: “subdivided into compartments”. This is unclear, what do you mean?

It is at line 40, not 49. It was: “Any budget can be further subdivided in compartments, modelled with a great variety of conceptualisations”. Is in the new manuscript: “Any budget term can be further subdivided, by separating it in parts, for instance discharge could be separated in surface, subsurface and groundwater discharge, modelled with various conceptualisations”

9.Line 49: typo, “in THE literature”. Also, this is a key point of the paper and some references are needed.

The introduction is revised and restructured.

10.Line 58: no parenthesis needed. Also, do the references provide a method? Explain.

Corrected accordingly. Yes, descriptions of the procedures are detailed there. In any case, we believe that the information given at section 3.2 is enough.

11.Line 60: “obsolete in part”: what do you mean? A discussion is needed

One important element of the innovative approach is the use of automatic calibration of theoretical semivariogram model parameters and others, which detailed in section 3.2. In the revised MS, we refer the section following this phrase, and now is: “obsolete in part as computing techniques have progressed (see section 3.2)”

12.Line 69: ARPS is a mesoscale model, not an effort to separate rainfall/snowfall and there are several models with similar capabilities (WRF, MesoNH, ect).

We revised this, now it is:

“Some interesting efforts present in literature are the psychrometric energy balance (e.g Steinacker, 1983; Harder and Pomeroy, 2013, 2014; Ye et al., 2013) and variations of the phase separation method proposed by the U.S. Corps of Engineers (Army, 1956; Rohrer, 1989). Other solutions can be found in meteorological models like ARPS (Xue et al., 2000, 2001) and WRF (Dudhia et al., 2005; Caldwell et al., 2009).”

13.Line 80-84: this sentence is colloquial, please rephrase (e.g. In this study we use discharge measurements at n locations to calibrate a hydrological model of the whole catchment)

Thank you, we revised the sentence. In the revised MS, it is: “Here we use discharge measurements at three stations to calibrate and validate discharge estimation of the whole basin using a hydrological model.”

14.Line 86: “processes that have to be partitioned”, what do you mean?

The phrase is unnecessary. We eliminated it.

15.Line 88: “physical knowledge” of what?

Revised to “knowledge of the physical process”

16.Line 96: here you need to give a hint on how your methodology works (i.e. “we provide a unique way ... based on ...”)

In the revised MS, it is changed to: “we provide a way to close water budget in the absence of ET and water storage measurements based on the combination of Priestley-Taylor (Priestley and Taylor, 1972) and Budyko hypothesis (Budyko, 1978) at any space-time scale.”

17.Line 118: “if not impossible”. I agree that the NewAGE system is a useful tool but I disagree on the fact that the analysis performed here are impossible to perform with other tools!

We removed this phrase.

18.Line 131, missing comma (“4 and 5, respectively”)

Corrected accordingly.

19.Line 134: remove “where ... applied”, it’s redundant

Thank you, we remove it.

20.Line 136: typo, remove “the”

“the” is deleted.

21.Line 139: “the basin is covered by a DEM”, consider rephrasing (e.g. a DEM is available for the site)

Now it is: “20 X 20 metres DEM is available for the site”.

22.Line 143: “overall ...applications”, this sentence is useless unless you provide a comparison with the literature (or you justify why)

We removed the sentence.

23.Figure 1: panel a is copy-pasted from Google, the scale is not even visible and a reference is missing. Panel b is not labelled, the scale is also missing. Also, you say “two of the hydrometers” but I see two hydrometers in total in the map. Please

clarify

We improved the figure. The latitude and longitude are added (labeled). The two hydrometers were overlap at the confluence near to the outlet, and now we revised it for visibility.

24.Line 156: “for the modeling” of what?

“each component of the water budget” is added.

25.Line 156: “It offers”, what does “it” refer to? Clearly to NewAGE but the sentence does not sound correct

The sentence is revised for clarity.

26.Line 160: a brief overview of the processes is probably needed (the reader needs to understand without having to read Formetta et al.). Also, no colon needed before the references.

Please see the answer for reviewer 1, specific comment 9.

27.Line 170: “the methods for each term”, what does it mean?

Revised. Now it is: “the methods for modeling each term”

28.Line 177: “information” on what? Also, information are not “calculated” (hydrological variables maybe?), please revise

It was “In other words, even if information can be calculated at the pixel level, for instance by exploiting a detailed knowledge of topography, this information is subsequently coarse-grained to get single values for any HRU.”

Now revised as:

“In other words, even if hydrological variables can be calculated at the pixel level, for instance by exploiting a detailed knowledge of topography, it is subsequently coarse-grained to get single values for any HRU.”

29.Line 181: what does “meaningful” mean? Distance from a river channel, slope/aspects within an HRU, small scale soil heterogeneities, and so on, result in

"meaningful" changes in ET which are not accounted for in this framework so please explain what "meaningful" means here.

We rephrase the sentence: "The rationale of this choice is to reduce to a minimum level of the spatial heterogeneity in the input data and processes, without eliminating all of it."

30.Line 191: "transverse them"?

Transverse them is appropriate when referring to a tree structure like rivers are. We added at the end of the phrase "in computation".

31.Line 192: "This approach ... outlet", unclear, please rephrase

Now the sentence is revised to: "This approach gives the modeling solution of Eq. (1) for any of the units independently, from the most uphill one to the outlet."

32.Figure 2: The procedure is clear in the text but not as clear in Fig. 2. The figure is small and full of text/names that makes no sense to the reader (e.g. data HM, interp FC, dat GC ...). The authors should consider to make a clear conceptual model, maybe simplifying and combining Figures 2, 3 and 4

We revised the figures accordingly. Now, the three figures are combined.

33.Line 251: WRF is one out of many are atmospheric models (see my comment on ARPS. Consider writing "as in atmospheric models (e.g. WRF, ARPS)"

We revised this line accordingly. See reply specific comment 12.

34.Line 256: "tends to be" or is?

Changed to "is".

35.Line 257: Temperature is not "modeled" is interpolated.

Corrected accordingly.

36.Line 251 (161): typo ("terms" should be "term")

Corrected.

37.Line 278: remove “at the moment” or replace with “here”. If you mean that the procedure will be improved in the future you need to explain it.

We replaced “at the moment” with “Here”.

38.Figure 3: see comment to Fig. 2

Corrected accordingly.

39.Line 309: consider rephrasing “ the possibilities ... include the simulation of snow metamorphism by means of a radiation budget”

We rephrased this sentence, and now it is: “NewAGE offers the possibilities to simulate snow metamorphism using radiation budget”

40.Line 315: typo (remove using)

“using” is Removed.

41.Line 410: the paragraph is unclear to me.

Yes, we revised the paragraph. Since the paragraph explains about two issues, which has been mentioned in the previous paragraphs, for clarity, we have taken it to the respective section above i.e L396 and L402.

42.Fig. 5: add label to panels (a, b, c)

Corrected accordingly.

43. Line 451: “results are found to be inconsistent”, any idea why? Need to elaborate

It is related to the nature of GOF index. The ME has different behavior from the other two (RMSE, and correlation). Though ME is a measure of mean bias, the opposite signs of the individual time step error values counter balance each other.

44.Line 470: “ The ... data”. Remove, this was explained in the methods.

Removed.

45. Fig. 6: Not sure I understand the difference between panel b and c. Both are

estimated rainfall, correct? Why, for the case SB37 for example, the main peaks are above 20 mm/h in panel a and below 15 mm/h in panel c?

Thank you for spotting this. We did error in combining the figures in Latex. In the revised MS, the correct figure is replaced.

46.Line 510: typo, “looking at”

Revised accordingly.

47.Table 3: consider combining with Table 2

It is more appropriate to combine Table 2 with table 4, and we maintain this as it is.

48.Line 530: clarify “best performing”

We used DK and LDK for precipitation temperature estimation, respectively. Hence, we put this in parenthesis.

49.Fig. 7: The font is too small, it's difficult to read axes and colorbar. Same for Fig. 8 and 9 (also correct HRu with HRU in the caption of Fig. 8)

We enlarge the plots for readability.

50.Line 556: no need to list all the kriging methods and their abbreviations again.

Thank you, we removed the list.

51.Line 559: “in order to ...make”, it’s colloquial, rephrase

We replaced this by: “To investigate the effect of precipitations generated using different kriging methods,

52. Line 564: “same model parameter values”, values are not the same, please discuss more

While there are small differences in the model optimized parameters value between the five simulations, description of this differences can be repetition of the table and does not add information to the MS.

53.Line 567: add reference to Fig 10 (otherwise it is cited after Fig. 11)

Figure 10 is added in the citation.

54.Line 568: “the best ... discharge”. See comment above. What do we learn from this result? Is the best interpolated rainfall fields really the best? Or the small number of meteo stations has led to a misleading result?

Please see answer to the general comment.

55.Line 571: define PBIAS (and KGE) abbreviations in the text.

We added a description of the GOF indexes in line 350. “The objective function used as standard in this paper is the KGE (Kling et al., 2012) which was considered more robust than the Nash-Shutcliffe efficiency. However, the goodness of fit was estimated by two other indicators, Pearson’s correlation coefficient and Percentage bias (PBIAS), all of which are described in Appendix B. Other statistical indicators of performances are specified case by case.”

56.Line 585: “The higher ... figure 10”, what is the basis for this assertion? You need to explain why DK should better capture the physics of the system.

The basis is the GOF results in table 5, and the long-term annual runoff estimation in figure 11. We referred the table and the figure in parenthesis.

Please see answer to the major comment 2.

57.Line 629: “used in literature”: references are needed here.

Thank you. We added: Aminzadeh and Or (2014); Cho et al. (2012); Viswanadham et al. (1991); Carmona et al. (2013); Cristea et al. (2012).

58.Fig. 10: from this figure it's very difficult to compare different kriging methods (the lines completely cover the observations). Consider showing less cases and add one/two panels with observations vs simulations. Also, the labels on the x axes are overlapping.

We improved the readability of this figure.

59.Fig. 11: difficult to read

We improved the readability.

60.Line 673: “ ET tends ...” start the new paragraph here

We started a new paragraph here.

61.Line 703: “ ET ... budget”. This is not true. In Fig. 16 ET is maximum in November. Does the model fails to simulate ET seasonality?

Please see the answer to major comment 1.

62.Line 715: do not start the sentence with "it" (it's not clear that you refer to Fig. 17 in the previous sentence)

The idea of this sentence is described by the sentence before. So, we removed this one.

63.Line 721: “interactions taking place”, worth adding a discussion on such interactions.

One alternative could be to rephrase as follows: “However, seeing it together with the other budget components highlights the interactions actually taking place between the runoff production and evapotranspiration with basin storage is an added value.”

64.Fig. 12: difficult to read

We improved the figure for readability.

65.Fig. 14: the gray band is not visible. Also, this figure does not add much information. Consider moving to the SI or combine with another figure (e.g. fig. 13)

The variability of alpha when considering different Budyko time is important information that we intended to show. However, we combined figure 13 and 14.

66.Fig. 15: difficult to read

We enlarge the figure to increase readability.

67.Fig. 16: How is it possible that transpiration is maximum in November when radiation and temperature should be limiting transpiration in the northern emisphere?

It is erroneous. Please see the answer to major comment 1.

68.Line 746: “Having ... method”, this is not a conclusion

It is revised like this: “To obtain accurate spatial time series of precipitation data for water budget modeling, the kriging procedure is validated using cross-validation methods. It emerges that OK and LOK performed better than DK and LDK in detecting the total mass of water that fell in the basin.”

69.Line 750: “However, ...runoff”, what is the conclusion here?

Since it is already described in line 762, this is deleted from here.

70.Fig. 17: I like this figure a lot. All the other figures should be as clear as this one.

Thank you, and we tried to improve all the others.

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